

An Approach to Obtain g-Functions using Artificial Neural Networks

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Abstract

G-functions are mathematical tools that link average borehole wall temperatures in borehole fields to heat injection and extraction rates. Various numerical, analytical and empirical ways to determine g-functions have been proposed by authors throughout the years. In this article, a way of assessing g-functions using artificial neural networks (ANN) is explored. This method is versatile enough to accommodate a varying number of boreholes and irregular borehole placements. The training of this ANN required half a million g-functions. Once trained, g-functions could be approximate in 0.19 second with an average precision of 0.285 % compared to reference g-functions.

1. Introduction

The objective is to measure the g-function approximation precision of ANN. Based on previous works (Dusseault and Pasquier 2018; Dusseault and Pasquier 2019), an architecture of three hidden layers with 200, 200 and 45 neurons respectively were chosen for the ANN (Fig. 1). It uses an input of 50 neurons to capture the geological and physical properties of the borehole field and uses 40 neurons to sample the resulting approximated g-function.

Fig. 1 Architecture of the ANN used in this work.

2. Methods and techniques

To validate the accuracy of the ANN's, 10 000 g-functions of 100 years were calculated. These approximations were compared against a benchmark of reference g-functions

obtained through another established assessment method (Dusseault and al. 2017).

3. Results

The following Table 1 shows the accuracies of the approximated g-functions for the best, median and worst of the validation cases. The average computation time of individual g-functions was 0.19 second.

Table 1 Accuracy of the approximated g-functions.

Relative accuracy	Value
Best case (%)	0.036
Median case (%)	0.285
Worst case (%)	2.450

4. Discussion

The configuration that led to the best case in Table 1 consists of a single borehole while the one that led to the worst case consists of 9 boreholes distributed at random on a 20 m by 25 m grid. This demonstrates that while ANN are promising, there is still work to be done to broaden their approximation qualities for more complex GHEs.

5. Conclusions

G-functions placed irregularly within geothermal heat exchangers can be approximated quite rapidly, in 0.19 second on average, by ANN without sacrificing much accuracy, with errors ranging from 0.036% to 2.45%. This was proven by a comparative benchmark of 10 000 approximations by the ANN against an already published g-function assessment method.

References

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